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EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF FUEL SLOSHING EFFECTS ON WING DYNAMICS

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Abstract: We provide an overview of a series of experimental tests performed by the Loads & Aeroelastics department at Airbus in support of a broader research activity, aiming at modelling the dissipative effects of fuel sloshing on the dynamic behavior of wing-like structures. We describe the test setup, its similarity with the actual wing-structure of a large civil aircraft, the scaling rules applied, the measuring equipment and the practical considerations which drove the design of the test rig. The free vibration of this wing-like structure is compared for cases with and without sloshing, showing the potential of exploiting the dissipation inherent to the fluid structure interaction process for dynamic load alleviation.

1 INTRODUCTION

The modelling of fluid free surface in containers is of interests in various fields of the aerospace industry. For modern satellites, the design is often driven towards lightweight structures, high pointing accuracy and long life expectations (Ref. [1]). These can result in relatively large proportion of the overall weight being allocated to the liquid propellant. Typical aerospace launchers also have a high ratio of payload to propellant mass (1:20 for the European Ariane 6, Ref. [2]). Therefore the movement of the liquid fuel within its containers can significantly affect the dynamical behaviour of these systems, during in-orbit controlled manoeuvres and atmospheric gust encounters in the launch phase. Extensive analysis of the environment and the modelling for space applications is provided in Ref. [3], [4] and [5].

In the field of aircraft design, the study of fuel movement within tanks is of paramount importance for the design of the fuel management control system, the evaluation of the handling characteristics of the aircraft and ultimately the assessment of the structural response of the containment structure (Ref. [6] and [7]). Other specialized applications are related to transport of non-flammable liquids, such as water, for firefighting purposes (Ref. [8]). The fuel sloshing effects on the aeroelastic response of aircraft structures have also been studied, but analysis is generally focused on the changes in the flutter boundaries when compared with dry-tank configurations (see for example Ref. [9]). To the knowledge of the authors, no attempt has been made

to investigate the effects of sloshing on the airframe response to discrete gust and continuous turbulence.

Hence, as part of a wider project, a test campaign has been carried out at the Airbus Proto-space facilities in Filton. This aimed at investigating the effect of fuel sloshing on the dynamic behaviour of wing-like structures. The work has been used in support of the EU H2020 proposal - SLOWD (SLOshing Wing Dynamics), involving a consortium of 10 partners from both academia and industries. The objective of this preliminary campaign is to prove that fuel sloshing affects significantly the damping characteristics of a free-vibrating cantilever beam, and therefore has the potential of alleviating dynamic loads if taken into account in the modelling. Furthermore the test data are to be used to the validation of numerical models to analyse the coupled behaviour. In order to achieve conditions close to limit, the cantilever is forced into a deflected shape and quickly released. The setup is a simplified, small-scale version of a test performed on a partial wing-box specimen at Airbus as presented in [10].

The fluid motion in the tank and the accelerations of the beam are analysed to understand the dissipative effects of liquid sloshing. The setup is considered representative of an airliner with fuel in its outer wing-tank, undergoing dynamic excitations. In fact typical acceleration measurements at the free-end are of the order of 10g, which are comparable with those derived for limit gusts on civil passenger airplanes.

Exploring the potential benefits of sloshing to aircraft design is also motivated by applications in other fields of engineering, where the dissipative effects due sloshing are exploited in tuned liquid dampers. These are tanks, partially full of liquid, whose purpose is to increase the damping of a structure by using the free surface motion of the fluid to counter any excitation. These devices have already found application in reducing the vibration in tall towers (see Ref. [11]). Similar devices are the anti-roll tanks that can be employed on ships (Ref. [12]). In this respect, the acceleration direction is peculiar to aircraft wings, since the main component acts perpendicular to the free surface.

The paper is organised as follows:

- A) We give an overview of the experimental setup, describing how the laboratory tests relate to the actual wing structure of a large passenger aircraft (Section 2) and describe the rationale for the various types of test performed.
- B) The processing of the acquired sensor data is presented in Section 3 together with details of the video imaging process used for the liquid free surface.
- C) Section 4 present the main results and conclusion of the test cases analysed, in particular comparisons between dry (no sloshing) and wet (with sloshing) cases are presented.

Finally the conclusive section gives an overview of the activity for the EU H2020 project SLOWD, planned to start in September 2019.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The main structural member is a cantilevered steel beam of 2.35m span (scale 1:5 w.r.t a single aisle airliner wing). A water tank is mounted onto the beam at the free-end side, spanning 0.7m, as shown in the figure 1. The quick release mechanism (shown in the bottom right insert of figure 1) is employed to pull the free-end down, to a condition close to maximum elastic stress in the beam but still within the geometrically linear regime (the tip deflection is <5% of

the span), and suddenly released. The free oscillation of the system are then monitored by the various sensors and the fluid motion is imaged by a high-speed camera.

The analysis of such type of couple fluid-structure system is not available in literature. In fact, the nature of the excitation applied to the fluid by the structure is peculiar to aircraft wing (or lifting surface) applications, in that it:

- is predominantly vertical, in direction perpendicular to the free surface.
- is of periodic nature, and not limited to a single impact event.
- can reach high acceleration levels (well above gravity), leading to the liquid departing from the bottom of the tank.

In space applications the sudden deceleration at the separation of a launcher stage can lead to severe impact forces, but these are generally resolved to a single event as opposed to the cyclic wing oscillations which are repetitive in nature. Furthermore the shape of the tanks in launchers is significantly different from those in aircraft wings.

Figure 1: Experimental Rig

The experimental configuration is designed to be similar to a real wing geometrically (span-wise position, width and height of the tank); to achieve vertical accelerations of the same order of magnitude of limit design cases of an airliner wing ($\sim 10g$) and such that the ratio of liquid and solid masses ($\sim 10\%$) is representative of typical design conditions.

The tank is divided in seven sealed compartments, to mimic the typical internal geometry of a wing tank which includes ribs. There are no openings on interior walls, to reduce the complexity of the fluid flow, as these are assumed to have secondary effects for primarily vertical excitations. The tank is mounted on the cantilever at an angle so that in the initial deflected position the tank bottom (and roof) are horizontal. The tank is attached to the beam at four point (see Figure 1 bottom left) by pin-joints. This allows for minimal transfer of longitudinal forces during the free oscillations, so that the tank can be assumed rigid in first approximation if the deflection of the beam is limited to the linear deformation regime.

By design the overall setup is configured to limit three-dimensional effects in both the motion

of vibrating structure and the fluid flow in the tank, to ease the characterisation of the coupled system. It is also important to notice that the total mass of the system can be controlled by the ballast placed beneath the tank on the underside of the cantilever (Figure 1 bottom centre).

2.1 Construction and Instrumentation

The *cantilever* is a commercially available H-section steel beam, with designation 127x76x13. The H section allows for easy mounting of the tank above the flanges and is approximately three-times stiffer in the horizontal than in the vertical direction. This feature limits unwanted in-plane oscillation of the beam. The fixed-end of the cantilever is clamped to a steel frame approximately two-order of magnitudes heavier than the beam to avoid dynamic coupling.

The *tank* is made of Tufnol[®] composite laminates, to allow for stiff, lightweight and waterproof construction. The roof is bolted to the main body and equipped with a rubber gasket to avoid leakages. All edges are sealed with transparent silicon. The maximum capacity of the tank is 15% of the cantilever mass when filled with water, but all tests are performed in condition of partial-fill.

The *Strain gauges* at the fixed-end (root) of the cantilever are used to measure the applied deflection prior to test execution and the bending moment during the free vibration. They are mounted symmetrically on the front and rear flanges of the beam, so that unwanted in-plane oscillation can be detected.

The *accelerometers* are glued on the web of the beam at two span-wise locations, directly underneath the tank inboard and outboard closing walls. They used to monitor the motion of the system in vertical and span-wise and fore/aft directions.

The *force transducers* are located at the base of the tanks at each of the four attachment points (see insert in Figure 1). They work under compression (and need pre-loading) and measure the incremental force transferred between the tank and the beam during the oscillations.

Figure 2: Video Imaging Setup

A *high-speed camera* (and specialised lighting) is used to record the fluid motion in the tank, an particularly the displacement of the liquid/gas interface (free surface). Videos are taken at 3000 frame-per-second. The camera and lighting setup is shown schematically in Figure 2.

2.2 Test Matrix

Preliminary tests.

A static loading test is performed to determine the overall stiffness of the cantilever. Additional tests are carried out to characterise the dynamic response of the dry and wet structure (output-only tap-tests), to measure ambient noise and ensure no dynamic coupling with support heavy frame. Specific tests, with close-up view on the two outermost tank compartments are also performed to analyse the qualitative differences between water (which is used for the majority of the tests) and kerosene.

Free-release tests.

The main set of tests are free-releases performed at various fill-levels with water in the tank, ranging between 20% and 80% at 10% increments. The overall mass of the system is kept constant via ballast weights and each test is repeated three times to assess repeatability. Baseline tests are also performed with a solid mass housed in the tank instead of water, representative of the current industrial techniques for loads modelling.

Parametric Variations.

Greatest sloshing effects are expected for the 50% fill level case, hence several single-parameter variations are performed starting from this condition:

1. Drying the tank roof innerside before each repetition.
2. With/without intermediate walls (ribs).
3. With obstacles below and above the free surface to perturb the liquid motion.
4. Tilting the tank so that the initial orientation of the bottom (and roof) is not horizontal.
5. Filling the tank with kerosene instead of water.

This paper presents the results of the main free-release tests at 50% fill-level in comparison with the baseline solid-mass case. Additionally the corresponding perturbations as per Bullets 1 and 2 above are analysed. The relevance of drying the tank roof (Bullet 1) is linked to the behaviour of the free-surface during the first cycle of oscillation and is described more in details in Section 4.2. A more in-depth analysis of a wider range of tests is presented in Ref. [13].

3 DATA PROCESSING

Data acquisition for all dynamic tests is performed at 1kHz; the motion and strain signals are synchronised for each test repetition. Video images of the liquid motion are taken for each tests repetition, but the high-speed camera is not synchronised with other the sensors.

3.1 Accelerometers, Strain Gauges, Force Transducers

Due to the manual activation of quick-release mechanism, the lag between the start of the recording and the actual release of the beam is not constant between test repetitions. The systematic synchronisation of the time series is achieved by maximising the cross-correlation function $C(t)$, given by

$$C(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} y_1(\tau)y_2(\tau + t)d\tau \quad (1)$$

where $y_1(t)$ and $y_2(t)$ are two generic time signals.

Figure 3: Accelerometer - 50% Fill-Level (Clean)

Figure 4: Strain Gauge - 50% Fill-Level (Clean)

Figure 5: Force Transducer - 50% Fill-Level (Clean)

All signals are low-pass filtered at 60Hz to remove noise and isolate the fundamental vibration modes of the system. Finally, standard Fast Fourier Transform is performed to analyse the frequency content of the time histories. Additional processing is required for the force transducers. As it can be seen in the bottom left of Figure 1, these are capacitors which can measure compressive load only. Therefore they are preloaded so that they remain under compression for the entire duration of the experiments. This preload is not known. Due to the symmetry of the configuration is assumed that the initial load on each of the four transducer is equal to one-fourth

of the weight of the tank. The force signals between the start of the recording and the quick release is averaged and this average value is removed from the signal.

Figure 3, 4 and 5 present the results from three repetition of the 50% fill-level case with "clean" roof (see Section 4.2.1 for more details). Both the strain gauge and accelerometer data present high level of repeatability. In Figure 5 a drift at the tail end of the signals is observed between different test repetitions, which could be explained by the fastener used to keep the sensor in compression loosening during the free oscillations.

3.2 Video Imaging

Figure 6 shows an example of the video imaging of the flow acquired during the experimental campaign. The setup described in Section 2 is used for the overall view on the full experiment, with the seven compartment of the tank in the field of view of the camera. The insert shows a close-up view of one of the bays, achieved after repositioning of the camera and focussing the high-intensity lights.

Figure 6: Video Imaging - Example

Following initial trials, it was established that the overall view was sufficient to identify the main characteristics of the flow, while allowing to establish the different flow regimes in the various compartment of the tank. Therefore this view was used systematically in conjunction with all the quantitative measurements. A limited number of qualitative tests was performed in the preliminary phase, with focus on the analysis of the characteristics of flow and particularly the onset of free surface motions during the first cycle of oscillation.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Free Vibration Response

The types and installations of all sensors are designed with the purpose of providing a means to validate isolated numerical models for the fluid and structural dynamics first, and eventually of the coupled system. In fact the acceleration signals can be used to excite an isolated rigid tank and to study the sloshing flow, as well as the dynamic response of a flexible beam. The force transducer and strain gauge readings can then be used for the validation of those models.

Figure 7 and 8 present the results from a single repetition of a variety of tests:

Accelerometer @ Free-End

Figure 7: Accelerometer - Various Test Cases (50% Fill Level)

Strain Gauge @ Root

Figure 8: Strain Gauge - Various Test Cases (50% Fill Level)

- Clean roof, the lid is removed for each test trial and all water drops are removed from the tank roof
- Drop Impact, the tank roof is wet and drops hit the free surface during the initial oscillation
- Clean Roof - Unbaffled, similar to "Clean Roof" but all internal partitions are removed from the tank
- Solid Mass, the sloshing liquid is replaced with a solid mass of the same weight

In general all cases with liquid do not present noticeable differences in the time histories and also the amplitudes of their Fourier transforms are similar. The solid case instead, as expected, exhibits a considerably lower damping of the oscillation compared with the liquid, also apparent from the amplitude of the first modal frequency around 7Hz in the bode plots. The frequency-domain results compare well with the initial Finite Element model developed to design the experiments. Table 1 lists the first four modes identified by numerical modal analysis, the first and fourth modes are consistent with the experimental data, with the second transverse bending particularly pronounced in the strain measurements with liquid (Figure 4).

Mode	f [Hz]	Description
1	7.25	1 st Transverse Bending
2	19.14	1 st In-Plane Bending
3	22.45	Local Tank Mode
4	44.24	2 nd Transverse Bending

Table 1: Numerical Modal Analysis Results

4.2 Flow Regimes

4.2.1 Initial Half-Cycle

The sequence of images in Figure 9 shows the different behaviour of kerosene and water observed in the preliminary testing phase. The images are ordered by increasing time from top to bottom and present comparison of the free surface motion for kerosene (left), water (middle) and the qualitative acceleration time history (right) at the free-end of the cantilever, during the first half-cycle of oscillation.

Immediately after the quick-release the fluid in the tank experiences "augmented gravity" due to the tank being accelerated upwards by the oscillation of the beam. During the first quarter-cycle there is minimal fluid motion, but three distinct effects are observed. First, the free-surface starts drifting towards the free-end of the cantilever (right hand-side in Figure 9), as a result of the centripetal acceleration experienced by the tank, in this respect the behaviour of both kerosene and water is similar. Second, due to adhesion effects, the free surface of the liquid is elevated in small regions close to the tank walls; these evolve into gravity waves, which are more pronounced in the case of kerosene, due to lower surface tension compared to water and therefore greater initial elevation. Third, due to cohesion effects, water tends to collect in the form of drops on the tank walls (and the roof in particular), which is not the case for kerosene; these drops fall and impact the free surface creating the crater-like structure that can be seen forming in Figure 9 - top middle.

After the first quarter-cycle the acceleration of the tank changes direction, and the fluid experiences a short transition phase of reduced gravity eventually reaching zero-g until the acceleration reverts direction and starts to push the liquid upwards (inverted gravity). For kerosene the free surface perturbations, initiated by the elevation at the side walls, evolve into Rayleigh-Taylor (RT) instabilities (Ref. [14]) which eventually assume the finger-like structure shown in Figure 9 - bottom left. These structures are typical of conditions in which a heavy fluid is accelerated towards a lighter one (liquid and air in the case under consideration), and are due to the opposing effects of buoyancy and inertia forces. For water instead, the free surface is significantly perturbed by the falling drops detaching from the roof, as can be seen in Figure 9 - middle centre and bottom centre.

4.2.2 Free Oscillations

During the second half of the first cycle, the flow becomes aerated following the impact with the roof. From the acquired images there does not seem to be a major difference between the dry-roof case (representative of kerosene-like behaviour) and the case with drop impact (water). Figure 10 shows the flow configuration at the end of the first oscillation cycle (≈ 0.15 s after the release), comparing the case with dry-roof at the top and drop-impact at the bottom. The flow

Figure 9: First Half-Cycle Flow

continues to be quite complex to characterise for several cycles, with no clear interface between air and water, indicating that both three-dimensional effects and air-entrainment are likely to influence this flow regime.

Figure 10: End of First Cycle - Dry Roof vs Drop Impact

Finally, after eight to nine cycle the liquid starts to settle at the bottom of the tank and a more defined free-surface become again identifiable in the video recordings. Figure 11 shows the flow configuration at the end of the ninth cycle, comparing the case with dry-roof at the top and drop-impact at the bottom.. There are still appreciable differences in the flow, but it can noticed that at least in some of compartments (e.g. the third cell from the left) the configuration of the free surface is similar in both tests.

Figure 11: End of Ninth Cycle - Dry Roof vs Drop Impact

4.2.3 Additional Remarks

From the analysis of the images it is evident that in the case of kerosene, which is of obvious relevance for aircraft applications, the response of the system during its initial oscillation is governed by the RT instability of the free surface. The first peak in the acceleration time histories is of interest for loads modelling, as it is often associated with the design loads for discrete gust events. Classic theoretical analysis of RT instability (see Ref. [14]), based on small perturbation theory, provide an indication on the wave number k (or spacial frequency) of the perturbation of the free surface that are most likely to evolve into the finger-like structure observed during the experiments. In fact, when considering the effect of surface tension γ , the growth rate of the perturbation (in time) can be expressed as a function of the density of the light and heavy fluids (ρ_1 and ρ_2), gravity g and the wave number, as:

$$n^2 = \left(A - \frac{\gamma k^2}{\rho_2 + \rho_1} \right) g k \quad (2)$$

where A is the Atwood number, defined as:

$$A = \frac{\rho_2 - \rho_1}{\rho_2 + \rho_1} \quad (3)$$

Equation 2 has a maximum for

$$k_* = k_c / \sqrt{3} \quad (4)$$

where

$$k_c = [(\rho_2 - \rho_1)g/\gamma]^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

Then the corresponding wavelength of maximum growth rate can be calculated as:

$$\lambda_{max} = 1/k_* \quad (6)$$

Liquid	ρ_2 [kg/m^3]	A	k_* [m^{-1}]	k_c [m^{-1}]	λ_{max} [m]
Water	1000	0.998	214.11	370.85	0.005
Kerosene	790	0.997	360.94	625.17	0.003

Table 2: RT Instability - Wavelengths for Max Growth

Assuming a typical air density and surface tension values for water and kerosene, the wavelength for maximum growth rate is calculated for both liquids in Table 2. These wavelengths are similar in magnitude to the elevation of the free surface observed near the tank walls at rest. As the evolution of the RT instability is a highly non-linear phenomenon, the applicability of small-scale results to full-scale remains an open point.

Also on the scalability of the results, it is common practice to design scaled sloshing tests enforcing Froude similarity (see [6]), which implies the flow being driven by gravitation forces. This is certainly the case for tanks undergoing excitations parallel to the free surface, causing the formation of gravity waves. Defining the Froude number as:

$$Fr = \frac{U}{\sqrt{gL}} \quad (7)$$

leads to the following scaling rules for length L , time T , velocity U , acceleration A and frequency f :

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{L_m}{L_f} &= s \\ \frac{T_m}{T_f} &= \sqrt{s} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where the subscripts m and f in Equations 8 indicate the test model and full scale respectively, and s is the geometric scale factor. Table 3 lists the relevant parameter required for Froude similarity in comparison with what achieved in the tests.

	f_m [Hz]	U_m [m/s]	Fr
Required	3.35	4.65	1.92
Achieved	7.25	2.15	0.89

Table 3: Froude Similarity Parameters

The required Fr number is more than twice that achieved during the experimental campaign. With the available materials it was not possible to reach a closer similarity, as this would have required a bespoke cantilever design. Also a lower natural frequency of 3.35Hz would have implied a greater initial displacement of the free-end, possibly leading to geometrically non-linear oscillation of beam. The fact that the characteristic velocity achieved is considerably lower than that required by Fr similarity could indicate that the dissipative effects due to liquid impact are underestimated in the present work compared to full scale. It is noticed that the scaling rules (Equations 8) would lead to similarity also in terms of centrifugal acceleration component, not achieved with the existing setup.

5 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

We presented the setup and initial analysis of a series of tests aiming at understanding the effect of sloshing in flexible wing tanks. Comparison with current modelling techniques shows the

viability of exploiting the dissipative effects due to the fuel motion for aircraft loads calculation. These are to be addressed by the SLOWD project, part of the EU-funded H2020 program, starting in September 2019. The partners of the SLOWD consortium intend to perform additional experimental tests similar to those described here, but of increased complexity in terms of geometry and range of parameters. The ultimate goal is to test and model numerically the sloshing effects of a full-scale aircraft wing.

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